

EVALUATION OF THE EFFECT OF SPECIFIC HAEMOGRAM AND BIOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS ON MORTALITY AND MORBIDITY IN PATIENTS WITH GASTROINTESTINAL SYSTEM HAEMORRHAGE

Keywords

Gastrointestinal bleeding,

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to investigate whether demographic, clinical and laboratory parameters have an effect on the mortality and morbidity of patients diagnosed with gastrointestinal system (GIS) bleeding in the emergency department. Our study was performed retrospectively in 113 patients with GI bleeding admitted to the emergency department between 01.06.2018-01.06.2019. Gender, age, presenting complaint, comorbid diseases and drug use, bleeding site, laboratory parameters, endoscopy findings, hospitalisation unit and mortality status were analysed. Kolmogorov-Smirnov, Mann Whitney-U, Chi-square, Fisher Exact and logistic regression analyses were used to analyse the data. The median age of the patients was 67 years and 61.9% were male. Comorbidities were found in 67.3% of the patients. The frequency of ulcerative colitis, haemorrhoids and other comorbidities was found to be high in patients with lower GI bleeding ($p < 0.05$). While the frequency of haematemesis and melena was significantly higher in patients with upper GI bleeding, haematochezia was significantly higher in patients with lower GI bleeding ($p < 0.05$). In our study, median values of Hb 9 g/dl, Hct 27.5%, MPV 10.4 μ l, platelet 225 $\times 10^3/mm^3$ were found. No correlation was found between the level of GI bleeding and mortality and Hb, Hct, MPV and platelet values ($p > 0.05$). Creatinine 0.8 mg/dl, BUN 24 mg/dl, BUN/creatinine ratio 26 were found at median values in our study. No correlation was found between the level of GI bleeding and creatinine level ($p > 0.05$). BUN level and BUN/creatinine ratio were found to be significantly higher in patients with upper GI bleeding ($p < 0.05$). It was found that 47.8% of the patients were hospitalised in the ward and 52.2% in the intensive care unit. In our study, mortality rate was 4.4% and no single factor was found to affect mortality alone ($p > 0.05$). In patients with GI haemorrhage, many factors were found to have an effect on the patient's clinic, but not on mortality. This may be related with the number of patients with mortal course. Therefore, larger case series are needed.

INTRODUCTION

Gastrointestinal system (GIS) haemorrhage represents a significant proportion of emergency department (ED) admissions. Both the frequency of occurrence and the fatal outcome increase the importance of GI haemorrhage.¹⁻²

Although there are intercommunity variations in GI haemorrhage, it occurs at a rate of 100-150 per 100,000 population.³⁻⁵

In clinical practice, the GI tract is divided into two sections, the upper and lower. The area above the ligamentum flavum is defined as the upper GIS and the area below the ligamentum flavum is defined as the lower GIS. In fact, the area defined as the upper GI tract refers to the area that can be assessed by endoscopy.⁶ Eighty percent of bleeding comes from the upper GI tract and 20 percent from the lower GI tract.⁴⁻⁵⁻⁷

The most common cause of upper GI bleeding is peptic ulcer (PU) with a frequency of 67%.⁸⁻⁹ Clinically it often presents as melena and haematemesis.⁶ Although rectal examination and demonstration of haematemesis with a nasogastric tube are sufficient for diagnosis in patients with upper GI bleeding, endoscopy is recommended to demonstrate the bleeding focus, clarify the etiology of the bleeding and intervene if necessary.¹⁰⁻¹¹

Lower GI haemorrhage is mostly associated with age and most are chronic. The most common

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causes of acute lower GI bleeding are diverticular disease (26%), benign anorectal disease (17%), colitis (14%) and haemorrhoidal bleeding (12%).¹²

While 80% of GI bleeding stops spontaneously, 20% require intervention.¹³⁻¹⁵ The incidence of recurrent GI bleeding after treatment is 3.3% in the short term and 20-30% in the long term. Recurrent GI haemorrhage after initial treatment may require surgery in 15-30% of cases and mortality is higher. The most important consideration in patients with GI bleeding is to stabilise haemodynamics as soon as possible.^{13,16} Identifying the cause of bleeding and stopping the bleeding is the most important point to achieve and maintain stability.¹⁷

We aimed to investigate the effect of demographic characteristics, additional comorbidities, endoscopy results, bleeding focus, blood urea nitrogen (BUN)/creatinine ratio, prothrombin time (PT), activated partial thromboplastin time (aPTT), haematocrit (Htc), platelet count and mean platelet volume (MPV) on mortality and morbidity in patients diagnosed with GI bleeding in the emergency department (ED).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Our study was carried out retrospectively with 113 patients after the approval of Hatay Mustafa Kemal University Non-Interventional Research Ethics Committee (with decision number 02 dated 05.09.2019).

It was performed in patients with GI bleeding who applied to the emergency department of Tayfur Sökmen Campus, Health Practice and Research Hospital between 01.06.2018-01.06.2019. Patient data were obtained from the hospital automation system and patient cards.

Patients over the age of 18 who had melena, haematemesis or haematochezia on physical examination according to the scan results of the hospital information processing system and who were definitively determined to have bleeding of non-GI bleeding origin or who were definitively diagnosed with GI bleeding by endoscopy and colonoscopy were included in the study. Patients under 18 years of age, patients with a suspected diagnosis of GI bleeding and patients with missing laboratory data were excluded from the study.

Gender, age, presenting complaint/symptom, known comorbid disease and drug use, bleeding site, Hb, Htc, MPV and platelet amount, BUN and creatinine, international correction ratio (INR), aPTT, PT endoscopy and colonoscopy findings,

hospitalisation unit and mortality were recorded.

Statistical analyses were performed with IBM SPSS software version 22.0. The conformity of the data to normal distribution was determined by Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. Since the parameters did not conform to normal distribution, median and interquartile range (IQR) were used for descriptive statistics. Mann Whitney-U test was used to compare two independent groups. Pearson Chi-square and Fisher Exact test were used to compare frequency data between two categorical variables. Logistic regression analysis was used to analyse the factors affecting mortality. A value of $p < 0.05$ was accepted as statistically significant in the analyses.

RESULTS

The total number of cases in our study was 113 and the median age was 67 (IQR:28) years. 70 (61.9%) of the cases were male. Upper GI bleeding was observed in 102 cases (90.3%) and lower GI bleeding in 11 cases (9.7%). Age and gender were not correlated with the level of GI bleeding ($p > 0.05$). The frequency of ulcerative colitis, haemorrhoids and other comorbidities was found to be significantly higher in patients with lower GI bleeding ($p < 0.05$).

In our study, 83 (73.5%) of 113 patients were found to be on medication, 19 (16.8%) were on anti-aggregants, 4 (3.5%) on anti-coagulants, 15 (13.3%) on NSAIDs and 80 (70.8%) on at least one of the other drugs. No correlation was found between drug use and the level of GI bleeding ($p > 0.05$) (Table 1).

In our study, haematemesis was present in 38 (33.6%), melena in 79 (69.9%) and haematochezia in 12 (10.6%) of 113 patients. While the frequency of haematemesis and melena was significantly higher in patients with upper GI bleeding, haematochezia was significantly higher in patients with lower GI bleeding ($p < 0.05$) (Table 2).

In our study, the median HB value was 9 g/dl (IQR: 3.4 g/dl), the median Hct value was 27.5 (IQR: 9.6), the median MPV value was 10.4 μ l (IQR: 1.6 μ l) and the median platelet value was 225 $\times 10^3/\text{mm}^3$ (IQR: 158 $\times 10^3/\text{mm}^3$). No correlation was found between the level of GI bleeding and HB, HCT, MPV and platelets ($p > 0.05$).

In our study, the median value of BUN was 24 mg/dl (IQR: 23.9 mg/dl), the median value of creatinine was 0.8 mg/dl (IQR: 0.5 mg/dl) and the median value of BUN/creatinine ratio was 26 (IQR: 23.5) in 113 patients. In our study, no correlation was found between the level of GI haemorrhage and creatinine

level. BUN level and BUN/creatinine ratio were found to be significantly higher in patients with upper GI bleeding ($p < 0.05$).

In our study, the median aPTT was 30.4 s (IQR: 8.4 s), the median PT was 15 s (IQR: 4.4 s) and the median INR was 1.2 (IQR: 0.45). In our study, no significant correlation was found between the level of GI bleeding and aPTT, PT and INR levels ($p > 0.05$).

Endoscopy of 102 patients with upper bleeding revealed varices in 24 (23.5%), gastritis in 44 (43.1%), PU/duodenal ulcer in 36 (35.3%), malignancy in 6 (5.8%), erosive gastritis in 3 (2.9%) and angioectasia in 1 (35.3%) patient (Table 3).

In 36 patients with ulcer, the most common lesion stage was Forrest 3 (36%; $n:13$) and the Forrest distribution of the patients is presented in Figure 1.

The lesions detected in colonoscopy of 11 patients for lower GI bleeding were ulcerative colitis in 4 (36.4%), malignancy in 3 (27.3%), haemorrhoids in 2 (18.2%), diverticulosis in 1 (9.1%) and Crohn's disease in 1 (9.1%) (Table 4).

In our study, 54 (47.8%) of the total patients were hospitalised in the ward and 59 (52.2%) in the intensive care unit.

In our study, 108 (95.6%) of a total of 113 patients were discharged from hospital, while 5 (4.4%) died.

In our study, no correlation was found between mortality and age and gender ($p > 0.05$)

In our study, the presence of comorbidities was not found to be associated with mortality ($p > 0.05$)

In our study, no relationship was found between drug use and mortality ($p > 0.05$)

In our study, haematemesis, melena and haematochezia were not associated with mortality ($p > 0.05$)

In our study, no correlation was found between mortality and the level of GI bleeding ($p > 0.05$) (Table 5).

In our study, no correlation was found between mortality and endoscopically detected lesions in patients with upper GI haemorrhage ($p > 0.05$)

In our study, mortality was not correlated with Hb, Hct, MPV and platelet values ($p > 0.05$)

In our study, no significant correlation was found between mortality and BUN creatinine and BUN/creatinine ratio ($p > 0.05$)

In our study, no significant correlation was found between mortality and aPTT, PT and INR levels ($p > 0.05$).

In the logistic regression analysis performed in our study, no single factor was found to be effective on mortality ($p > 0.05$).

DISCUSSION

GI bleeding is an important cause of morbidity and mortality in patients admitted to the emergency department and diagnosed here. Although different causes lead to both upper and lower GI bleeding, the resulting blood loss results in mortality in case of delayed clinical intervention. In our study, we analysed these factors and their effects on morbidity and mortality.

GI bleeding can be seen in all age groups. It can be seen more frequently in advanced ages due to different underlying causes. In studies, different age ranges have been reported depending on the level of bleeding. It has been reported to be 43-72 years of age in cases with upper GI haemorrhage and 63-77 years of age in cases with lower GI haemorrhage (18). There are also publications showing that age has an effect on morbidity and mortality together with other causes and mortality increases with advancing age.¹⁵ In our study, the mean age was 67 years and no age difference was found between upper and lower GIS. However, an increase in mortality was found in older patients. Our findings were found to be compatible with the literature. This may be due to the deterioration of vascular structures with increasing age due to pathologies such as atherosclerosis, increased use of anti-aggregants and anticoagulants due to pathologies such as coronary artery disease (CAD) and cerebrovascular disease, increased use of steroid and NSAIDs due to osteoarthritis and arthritis. The main reason for the high frequency of lower GI bleeding in the elderly may be the fragility of the vascular walls and intestinal lining and the high frequency of malignancy. The fact that mortality is higher in the elderly may be related with comorbidities such as cirrhosis and high frequency of drug use and high non-response to treatment in these patients.

In studies, it has been reported that males have both lower GI bleeding and upper GI bleeding at a higher rate compared to

females.¹⁸ While the male-female ratio is more than 2 in cases with upper GIS haemorrhage, this ratio is 1.1-1.4 in cases with lower GIS haemorrhage. It is controversial whether gender is a risk factor for mortality in studies. While Köseoğlu et al. stated that being male was a risk factor for mortality, Aydın et al. stated that it was not a risk factor. Aydın et al. stated that gender was not related with mortality in their study.¹⁹ In our study, 69.6% of the patients were male and it was found that gender was similar in patients with upper and lower GI haemorrhage and did not pose a risk for mortality. Similar to the literature, we found that male patients had GI haemorrhage more frequently. The reason for the higher rate of male patients in cases with GI haemorrhage may be related with the fact that men live more irregularly, consume cigarettes and alcohol more frequently and have a higher tendency towards malignancy, in addition to the risk of being a man in itself. The high male density in both upper and lower GI tract may have prevented the difference between the groups. The main reason for the lack of correlation between mortality frequency and gender is that the factors determining the patient's clinic are related with the amount of bleeding and general condition rather than demographic characteristics.

One of the factors affecting both prognosis and mortality in patients with GI bleeding is comorbid disease. Studies have reported that more than 70% of patients with GI bleeding have at least one comorbid condition (20-22). Many studies have reported that many comorbidities, especially liver pathology and related medication use, are risk factors for mortality.^{15,23} Klebl et al. reported that renal disease, cardiovascular disease and liver failure were associated with mortality, with the mortality rate increasing to 86% in patients with liver failure.²⁴ Lecleire et al. found that the mortality rate was 23.5% in patients with GIS bleeding with cirrhosis and 11.2% in patients without cirrhosis.²⁵ In a study of patients with lower GI bleeding, cardiovascular disease and cirrhosis were reported to increase the risk of death.²⁶ In our study, comorbidities were found in 67.3% of patients. Consistent with the literature, the most common comorbidities found in patients with upper GI bleeding were HT, DM and cirrhosis, whereas ulcerative colitis and haemorrhoids were found in patients with lower GI bleeding. We believe that some comorbid conditions do not affect bleeding, but some conditions increase bleeding either directly by disrupting vascular structure or indirectly by disrupting coagulation. As these factors affect both the upper and lower GI tract, we

believe that many comorbidities cause bleeding regardless of the level. The small number of cases with lower GI bleeding may have highlighted some comorbidities. We believe that patients with liver pathologies, such as cirrhosis and hepatitis, are associated with coagulopathy and severe bleeding, such as oesophageal varices, and are therefore more likely to die in intensive care. As the number of deaths was low, we believe that comorbidities did not affect mortality.

Some drugs are considered among the predisposing factors for upper GI bleeding. Anti-aggregant, anti-coagulant and NSAIDs are the most important of these drugs. It has been reported that the use of these drugs has become widespread over time and some drugs have been included in some scoring systems.²⁷ In studies, it was reported that the frequency of drug use in patients with upper GI bleeding reached 76%.²⁸ In patients with upper GI bleeding, it has been reported that the frequency of anti-aggregant use is between 30-54%, the frequency of NSAID use is between 25-49%, and the frequency of anti-coagulant use is between 7-8%.²⁰⁻²¹⁻²⁸ In several studies, it was reported that the mortality frequency was higher in patients using NSAIDs.²⁹ Hreinsson et al. stated in their study that the role of these drugs in lower GI bleeding was not as much as upper GI bleeding, but these drugs had a role in acute lower GI bleeding, especially diverticular.³⁰ In a study conducted in patients with lower GI bleeding, it was reported that anti-aggregant agents significantly increased the mortality frequency, while anti-coagulants decreased it at a low rate.²⁶ In our study, it was found that 73.5% of the patients used drugs, 16.8% used anti-aggregants, 3.5% used anti-coagulants and 13.3% used NSAIDs. The frequency of drug use was consistent with the literature. No correlation was found between drug use and GI bleeding level and mortality. We are of the opinion that drug use triggers bleeding, especially GI bleeding, but its effect on prognosis is lost with the detection of bleeding, discontinuation of drugs and replacement of the deficiency.

Patients with upper GI bleeding frequently present with melena and haematemesis, whereas patients with lower GI bleeding more frequently present with haematochezia. It has been reported that 45-66% of patients with upper GI bleeding present with melena and 9-33% with haematemesis, and melena and haematemesis develop together in the majority of cases.²²⁻²⁸ Barkun et al. reported that the presence of active melena, haematemesis and haematochezia was a risk factor for

mortality in patients with upper GI bleeding.¹⁵ In our study, haematemesis was present in 33.6%, melena in 69.9% and haematochezia in 10.6% of the patients. While the frequency of haematemesis and melena was significantly higher in patients with upper GI bleeding, haematochezia was significantly higher in patients with lower GI bleeding. In accordance with the literature, melena was the most common symptom in our study, and we believe that this may be related to the fact that both upper and lower GI tract present itself with melena. In addition, it should be kept in mind that while it is very difficult for bleeding from the lower GI tract to reach the upper segment, bleeding from the upper GI tract can only occur in very high volume bleeding. Although we would normally expect high mortality in high-volume haematemesis in oesophageal varices and haematochezia originating from the upper GI tract due to the high volume of haemorrhage, the fact that the patients were very frightened of the picture and presented without losing time may have affected the mortality.

It has been reported in many studies that the most common cause of upper GI bleeding in patients with upper GI bleeding is PU and this rate is between 38.2% and 51.6% (28,31). It has also been reported that the frequency of Forrest stage 3 haemorrhage is higher than other stages in patients with upper GI bleeding.³² It has been reported that oesophageal variceal haemorrhage varies according to the frequency of hepatitis, especially alcohol consumption, and is generally around 10-15%, and this rate increases to 30% in some countries where alcohol consumption is high. In a study conducted in France, where alcohol consumption is high, the rate of variceal haemorrhage in patients with upper GI bleeding was found to be 20.3%, which is relatively higher compared to the literature.³³ In lower GIS colonoscopy, it has been reported that diverticula ranked first with a rate of 27%(21,30). In their study, Sonnenberg et al. stated that peptic and duodenal haemorrhages had a greater risk in terms of mortality.³⁴ In our study, we found that the most common upper GI lesions were gastritis and PU/duodenal ulcer (most common Forrest stage 3), however, the frequency of variceal bleeding was higher than the literature. The most common lesions detected in lower GI bleeding were ulcerative colitis and malignancy. No correlation was found between mortality and endoscopically detected lesion. The high frequency of variceal bleeding may be related to the high rate of alcohol production and consumption in the culture of the region. In addition, since we are the only tertiary care centre in the region, the referral of

oesophageal variceal haemorrhage to our hospital for intervention may have increased the frequency of oesophageal variceal haemorrhage. The frequent use of endoscopy in both diagnosis and treatment and the stabilisation of patients in a short time after stopping bleeding by endoscopy may have affected the frequency of mortality. However, we believe that the recurrence of some haemorrhages and the development of mortality due to other diagnoses after discharge may have an effect on long-term mortality.

Studies related with upper GI haemorrhages have found that the mean Hb values in blood tests taken at the time of presentation to emergency services were 8.2 -9.9 gr/dl and the mean platelet values were found between 183-268 thousand in mm³.²²⁻³³ It was reported that patients with shock and low Hb levels had a more mortal course in patients with upper GI haemorrhage (15, 18 24Shah et al. found that for every 1-point decrease in incident Htc, mortality increased. 1.4-fold.³⁵ It has been reported that platelets with high MPV contain larger granules and provide thrombosis development and bleeding control at a higher rate.³⁶ In our study, the median value of Hb was 9 g/dl, the median value of Hct was 27.5%, the median value of MPV was 10.4 µl and the median value of platelet was 225 x10³/mm³. No correlation was found between Hb, Hct, MPV and platelets and GI bleeding level and mortality. In our study, we believe that Hb and Hct values decreased due to bleeding in accordance with the literature. We are of the opinion that existing platelets were used due to acute bleeding, and there may be variability in the MPV value of newly produced platelets. In addition, even if MPV increased due to bleeding in these patients, we are of the opinion that this would not be related neither with the bleeding focus nor with the patient's clinic nor with mortality. However, it should be kept in mind that the size of newly formed platelets may be effective on the reduction of bleeding. Since thrombocytopenia is one of the rare causes of GI bleeding, we believe that it was not statistically significant in our study. Although Hb and Hct levels may have developed acutely and rapidly in the upper GI tract and chronically and slowly in the lower GI tract, there may not have been a correlation between the level of bleeding and the values, since low levels developed in both.

The increase in BUN in patients with GI bleeding is not parallel to the increase in creatinine. It is caused by the breakdown of blood proteins that enter the intestine as a result

of bleeding by bacteria in the intestine and the reabsorption of the urea formed. In addition, the development of hypovolemia leads to an increase in BUN. Elevated serum urea and creatinine have been reported to be risk factors for high mortality.¹⁵⁻¹⁸ Chandnani et al did not report an association between BUN and creatinine levels and mortality in their study of patients with upper GI haemorrhage.¹⁸ In a study conducted by Kumar et al. in patients with upper GI bleeding, it was reported that patients with elevated 24-hour creatinine levels had a worse prognosis.³⁷ In our study, the median value of BUN was 24 mg/dl, the median value of creatinine was 0.8 mg/dl and the median value of BUN/creatinine ratio was 26. In our study, no correlation was found between GI bleeding level and creatinine level. In our study, no significant correlation was found between mortality and BUN, creatinine and BUN/creatinine ratio. In our study, in agreement with the literature, BUN increased more in patients with upper GI bleeding, which may be related to the fact that blood converted to urea by bacteria is digested in a larger area and the area that can be reabsorbed is larger. With increased blood loss, patients with high BUN and BUN/creatinine ratio may have been followed in the ICU due to both the BUN load caused by the amount of blood digested and the higher BUN elevation caused by hypovolemia. We believe that the creatinine ratio did not change because this situation did not put additional stress on the kidney. Again, because of the low mortality rate, we believe that mortality is not related to BUN, creatinine and the BUN/creatinine ratio.

In studies performed in patients with GI haemorrhage, it was stated that patients with high INR level had a tendency to bleed. Chandnani et al. reported that INR was 1.2 in their study in patients with upper GI bleeding and did not report a relationship between INR and mortality.¹⁸ Klebl et al. reported that coagulopathy was associated with high mortality in upper GI bleeding.²⁴ In our study, the median value of aPTT was 30.4 s, the median value of PT was 15 s and the median value of INR was 1.2. In our study, no significant correlation was found between the level of GI bleeding and mortality and the level of aPTT, PT and INR. In our study, PT and INR levels were found to be significantly higher in patients hospitalised in intensive care unit.

Upper GIS originates in 80% and lower GIS originates in 20% of haemorrhages.⁴⁻⁵⁻⁷ Koch et al. reported that 75% of the cases were upper GIS and 25% were lower GIS.³⁸ In our

study, 8% of the cases were lower GIS bleeding. The high frequency of upper GI bleeding in our study may be due to the fact that the food habits of the region include more spices and alcohol, unlike other societies.

The rates of intensive care unit follow-up vary considerably in the studies in the literature. This rate varies between 11-70%.³⁹ In our study, 47.8% of the patients were hospitalised in the ward and 52.2% in the intensive care unit. This may be related with the fact that cases with upper GI bleeding are more intense and acute. In addition, the frequency of intensive care unit follow-up may be high because the patients were elderly and had comorbid pathology.

Despite innovations in medical and endoscopic treatments, the mortality rate in upper GI haemorrhage is still between 5-15%.⁴⁻²⁷⁻²⁹ In previous studies, it was reported that mortality in inpatients with upper GI bleeding was 1.8-16%, but mortality directly related with bleeding was 5.1%.²⁸⁻³⁸ Gölgeli et al. They found this rate to be relatively low (1.75%) compared to the literature.²⁸ Mortality rates in lower GI haemorrhage vary between 1.5% and 5% in most published series.¹⁻²¹ In our study, the mortality rate was 4.4% and no single factor affected mortality. Since our study included both upper and lower GI bleeding, mortality was higher in lower GI bleeding and there was no lower GI-related mortality in our study, the mortality rate can be considered compatible with the literature. In addition, since our hospital is the only tertiary care hospital in the province, sending selected cases, having adequate technical facilities and having specialised physicians may have reduced the mortality rate. We believe that there was no factor affecting mortality due to the low number of excised cases.

CONCLUSION

Although many factors have an effect on mortality in patients with GI haemorrhage, we found that these factors alone were insignificant in our study. HT, DM and cirrhosis were found most frequently in all haemorrhages. Hb and Hct levels were found to be significantly lower in patients hospitalised in intensive care unit. BUN level and BUN/creatin ratio were found to be significantly higher in patients hospitalised in intensive care unit with upper GI bleeding. In our study, mortality was not associated with BUN, creatinine and BUN/creatinine ratio.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest

related to this study.

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Table 1. Relationship between drug use and GI bleeding level

	TOTAL (n:113)	SECTION		p*
		Upper (n:102) n(%)	lower (n:11) n(%)	
Medicine	83 (73,5)	75 (73,5)	8 (72,7)	1.000
Anti-agreagan	19 (16,8)	18 (17,6)	1 (9,1)	0,687
Anti-coagulant	4 (3,5)	4 (3,9)	0 (0)	1.000
NSAİD	15 (13,3)	13 (12,7)	2 (18,2)	0,639
Other Medicine	80 (70,8)	72 (70,6)	8 (72,7)	1.000

*Fisher's Exact Test

Table 2. Relationship between symptoms and GI bleeding level

	Total(n:113)	Section		p*
		Upper (n:102) n(%)	lower (n:11) n(%)	
Hematemesis	38 (33,6)	38 (37,3)	0 (0)	0,015
Melena	79 (69,9)	76 (74,5)	3 (27,3)	0,003
Haematochezia	12 (10,6)	2 (2)	10 (90,9)	<0,001

*Fisher's Exact Test

Table 3. Endoscopic diagnoses

	N	%
Varis	24	23,5
Gastrit	44	43,1
Peptic/duedanal ulcer	36	35,3
Malignite	6	5,8
Eraziv bulbitis	3	2,9
Angioektazi	1	1,0

Figure 1. Forrest staging in patients with peptic/duodenal ulcer

Table 4. Colonoscopic diagnoses

	n	%
Ulcerative colitis	4	36,4
Malignite	3	27,3
Hemoroid	2	18,2
Diverticolysis	1	9,1
Crohn's disease	1	9,1

Table 5. Association of GI bleeding level with mortality

	Mortality		p*
	Alive (n:108) n(%)	Deceased (n:5) n(%)	
Upper GiS	97 (89,8)	5 (100)	1.000
Lower GiS	11 (10,2)	0 (0)	

*Fisher's Exact Test